

A Study on Customer Opinion for ATM Quality Services in Selected Public Sectors Bank with Special Reference to Dharmapuri

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Introduction and Design of the Study

Introduction

In banking industry, e-services are revolutionizing the way business is conducted. Electronic based business models are replacing conventional banking system and almost of banks are rethinking business process designs and customer relationship management strategies. It is also known as e-banking, online banking which provides various alternative e-channels to using banking services i.e. ATM, credit card, debit card, internet banking, mobile banking, electronic fund transfer, electronic clearing services etc. however, as per Indian e-banking scenario ATM is most acknowledged than other e-channels.

The history of ATM can be traced back to the 1960s, when the first ATM machine was invented by John Shepherd-Barron he was managing director of De La Rue Instruments. That machine used by Barclays Bank (Barclays Bank in Enfield Town in North London, United Kingdom) in 27 June 1967 (Wikipedia E-encyclopedia). However, the first bank to introduce the ATM concept in India was the Hong Kong and Shanghai Banking Corporation (HSBC) in the year 1987 followed by Bank of India in 1988. According to R.B.I. annual report (2008-09) almost commercial banks are providing ATM facilities to its customers and to date 27,277 ATMs installed by public sector banks and 15320 ATMs installed by private sector banks in India The Indian economy is emerging as a one of the strongest economy of the world with the GDP growth of more than 8% every year. A strongest banking industry is important in every country and can have a significant affect in supporting economic development through efficient financial service. Banking sectors play a vital role in growth and development of Indian economy

Objectives of the Study

- The main objectives of this study is to carry-on the brief on “customer atm quality service preference and survey of selected “Public sector banks” in Dharmapuri District.

- To understand the whole aspects of banking industry in India.
- To examine the extent of utilization of banks atm service by customers.

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, there has been a growing importance of service sector worldwide and in Indian context also this sector is gaining momentum. This indicates the growing demand for the service of banking and insurance sectors. This is due to the effect of the financial sectors reforms which has resulted in the increased competition among the banks. However, the human perceptions change from time to time and from individual to individual.

Conceptual Background of the Study

Introduction to Banking

Any company, which transacts the business of banking defined above is termed as banking company. In simple words, Banking can be defined as the business activity of accepting and safeguarding money owned by other individuals and entities, and then lending out this money in order to earn a profit. However, with the passage of time, the activities covered by banking business have widened and now various other services are also offered by banks. The banking services these days include issuance of debit and credit cards, providing safe custody of valuable items, lockers, ATM services and online transfer of funds across the country / world.

It is well said that banking plays a silent, yet crucial part in our day-to-day lives. The banks perform financial intermediation by pooling savings and channelizing them into investments through maturity and risk transformations, thereby keeping the economy's growth engine revving. Banking business has done wonders for the world economy. The simple looking method of accepting money deposits from savers and then lending the same money to borrowers, banking activity encourages the flow of money to productive use and investments.

Vision and Mission of SBI

Vision

- My SBI.
- My Customer first.
- My SBI: First in customer satisfaction

Mission

- We will be prompt, polite and proactive with our customers.
- We will speak the language of young India.
- We will create products and services that help our customers achieve their goals.
- We will go beyond the call of duty to make our customers feel valued.
- We will be of service even in the remotest part of our country

Symbol of State Bank of India

State Bank of India is a blue circle with a small cut at the bottom. It Was designed by Shepherd Kamath, an alumni of National Institute of Design, Ahmedabad.

Introduction to IOB

History

In 1937, Thiru M. M Chidambaranchettyar established the Indian Overseas bank to encourage overseas banking and foreign exchange operation IOB started up simultaneously at three bankers one each in karaikudi, Madras, and Rangeon. It brickly opened a branch in penangkualalumpur 11937 or 1941. The bank served the nattukottaichettiars who were a mercantile class that at the time had spread from chettinadu in Tamil Nadu. State to Ceylon Burma Malaya Singapore java Sumatra and sayon. In 1992 bank of commerce (BOC) a Malaysian bank, required United Asian Bank (UAB).

Interpretation

It is found from the table 4.2 shows that age group of the respondents out of 150 respondents, 33.33% of the respondents are in the age group of below- 30 years, 26.67% of the respondents are in the age group of 31- 40 years, 20% of the respondents are in the age group of 41- 50 years, 20% of the respondents are in the age group of above 51 years.

The above analysis shows that majority (33.33%) of the respondents are in the age group of below 30 years.

The above table 4.3 shows that educational qualification of the respondents 33.33% of the respondents are in the educational qualification of Up to H.sc, 26.67% of the respondents are in the educational qualification of illiterate, 20% of the respondents are in the educational qualification of Diploma level, 20% of the respondents are in the educational qualification of PG and above of the respondents.

The majority (33.33%) of the respondents are in the educational qualification of Up to H.sc. It is identified from table 4.9 shows that type of account of the respondents, 40% of the respondents are in the type of your bank of saving bank account, 26.67% of the respondents are in the type of your bank fixed deposit account, 20% of the respondents are in the type of your bank current account, 13.33% of the respondents are in the type of your bank recurring deposit account.

Majority (40%) of the respondents are in the type of your bank of saving bank account. From the analysis above table 4.24 of shows that respondents satisfaction level about the service quality of our bank, 33.33% of the respondents are highly satisfied, 26.67% of the respondents are highly – dis – satisfied, 20% of the respondents are satisfied, and 20% of the respondents are dis – satisfied.

Majority (33.33%) of the respondents are satisfaction level about the service quality of our bank are “highly satisfied”.

Findings

- Majority (66.67%) of the respondents are male when compared to female.
- The above analysis shows that majority (33.33%) of the respondents are in the age group of below 30 years.
- The majority (33.33%) of the respondents are in the educational qualification of Up to H.sc.
- It is concluded from the above analysis that maximum (33.33%) of the respondents under “agriculture” category.

- The majority (40%) of the respondents are in the income level of Rs.11, 000- Rs. 20,000 per month.
- The above analysis shows that the majority (46.67%) of the respondents are in the residing location of rural area.
- The above analysis shows that the majority (46.67%) of the respondents are in the prime bank of Indian bank.
- Majority (53.33%) of the respondents are in the nature of account is “Individual Account.”

Suggestions

- Customer satisfaction is the care of any banking institution satisfying the customer involves the provision of expected services faster.
- It suggested increasing the no.of delivery channels cite credit card, Debit card, ATM card, anywhere banking, Multiple delivery channels, Single window service, Mobile banking, Phone banking, E-banking and services at the door steps would improving the customer satisfaction and also increasing the number of customer.
- The response of the employees to the service request of the customers is a major area where more concentration is required by the employees, this would help the employees to carry out their services promptly and faster.
- To understand the customers needs and theirto help them in opening an amount for new clients, a “May I Help You” counter can be improved,.
- It suggested A separate enquiry cell can be opened in which an experienced employee can be placed.
- The banks can observe a specific day on every month as the day of “Customer meet”. This meeting can be utilized as an opportunity to have personal contract with the customers. This meet can help and in creating awareness on the new schemes introduced and guide them in choosing the right scheme based on their requirement. Above all such meets result in creating trend and loyalty.

Conclusion

The study could also re-establish the conclusions of the earlier studies that the customers consider the reliability dimension as the foremost important factor in banking service. This shows that, a part from availability of man, machines and other infrastructure the employees play a deterministic role in customer service. With better understanding of customers perceptions, the banks can determine the best actions required to meet the customers needs. They can understand their own strengths, weaknesses, identify opportunities and chart out proper awareness for further progress and improvement. This study also establish a strong relationship between the socio economic status of the customers and their satisfaction on the service quality.